

REACTION HOT PRESSING OF NIOBIUM ALUMINIDE-BASED COMPOSITES USING TREATED REINFORCEMENTS

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ABSTRACT

Intermetallics such as aluminides and silicides generally have low ductility and toughness at room temperature and poor creep resistance at elevated temperatures. In this investigation "treated" silicon carbide whisker and niobium particle reinforced niobium aluminide matrix composites have been fabricated by reaction hot pressing in vacuum. Elemental matrix powders react exothermally and form the niobium aluminide matrix *in situ*. Process optimization has led to the formation of Nb₃Al matrix, while reducing adverse reactions between the matrix and the reinforcements. The fabricated composites show relatively low hardness and higher toughness in comparison with the composites reinforced with the untreated whiskers.

INTRODUCTION

Aluminides and silicides are currently being considered for use in a wide variety of high temperature structural aerospace applications [1-8] because of their high melting point, relatively high strength, and low density. In general, these intermetallics lack ductility and toughness at room temperature because of their ordered structure. Thus, the use of these materials will largely depend on improving certain properties such as low temperature ductility, high-temperature strength and creep resistance [1-5,7]. Ductility and toughness of intermetallics at low temperatures have been improved in some systems such as Ni₃Al and Ti₃Al by microalloying [7,9-15] and macroalloying [9,10,16]. The creep resistance and toughness in some intermetallics have been improved by the use of suitable reinforcements [17-19].

Reinforcements can be used to improve the fracture toughness by providing a relatively weak interface that will lead to crack blunting and fiber pull-out. Studies have shown improvements in both room temperature ductility and high temperature creep resistance of MoSi₂ when reinforced with SiC whiskers (20 vol.%); room temperature fracture toughness increased from 5.32 MPa√m for the unreinforced material to 8.20 MPa√m for the reinforced material when produced by hot pressing [17,18]. Crack deflection has been observed as one of the toughening mechanisms [20]. Other possible mechanisms may include crack bowing, branching, bridging, and microcracking. The incorporation of niobium into the silicide matrix of Nb₅Si₃ by vacuum arc casting followed by hot extrusion and heat treatments to yield a higher aspect ratio niobium phase has led to an increase in fracture toughness from 1-3 MPa√m for monolithic Nb₅Si₃ to values exceeding 20 MPa√m for the composite as reported in the work by Mendiratta et al. [19]. Another system, MoSi₂ reinforced with 20 vol.% of niobium particles or niobium laminates also has shown improved toughness [21,22]. Ductile phase toughening is accomplished by ductile bridging of intact ligaments behind the crack tip i.e. ductile reinforcements help to blunt and retard crack propagation [23]. However, the reinforcements of the composites are not protected from reaction with the matrix at elevated temperatures. Thus, they do not have appropriate microstructures for thermal stability and are likely to have poor creep resistance at elevated temperatures.

The overall objective of our study is to improve both the room temperature ductility and toughness, and the high temperature strength and creep resistance of discontinuously reinforced niobium aluminide matrix composites. This paper deals with the fabrication and room temperature properties of the composites. Our approach is to provide suitable coatings for selected reinforcements, followed by reaction hot pressing in vacuum. Nb₃Al has been selected as the matrix because of its attractive high temperature properties [24]. It exists over a narrow composition range and has a melting point of 2333 K [25]. This material, like many other intermetallics, has limited ductility owing to its low symmetry complex crystal structure. Two different types of "treated" discontinuous reinforcements are to be incorporated into the matrix. The selected reinforcements are silicon carbide whiskers and niobium particles. The "treatments" are aimed at (a) providing protective coating for the reinforcements, thereby avoiding undesirable reactions with the intermetallic matrix and (b) tailoring the interfaces in the composite. The whisker reinforcement is to improve the high temperature strength and creep resistance. The room temperature ductility and toughness are expected to be improved by niobium particles providing ductile phase toughening. The tailored interface may provide additional toughening of the composite. An oxide coating has been selected, due to its chemical stability and the relative ease of obtaining it by high temperature exposure of the reinforcements in air. A uniform coating is desired on the reinforcements to provide adequate protection from the reaction with the matrix.

POTENTIAL REACTIONS

A thermodynamic study is performed using SOLGASMIX [26], a computer program to determine the chemical stability of the coated and uncoated reinforcements in the intermetallic matrix. The details are available elsewhere [27]. The SOLGASMIX analysis suggests the following: (a) that uncoated silicon carbide (whiskers), in the presence of elemental niobium and aluminum powders, readily dissociates into silicon and carbon which in turn react with niobium to form niobium carbides and silicides under hot pressing conditions. Elemental silicon is also expected to combine with aluminum to form a solid solution. Incorporation of the oxide coated silicon carbide whiskers and niobium particles shows enhanced chemical stability of the reinforcements with the aluminide matrix; interfacial reaction products may consist of NbO, SiO₂, Al₂O₃, NbO₂ or Nb₅Si₃.

EXPERIMENTAL WORK

FABRICATION OF COMPOSITES

Powder metallurgy (P/M) processing techniques were used for the fabrication of the composites; consolidation being accomplished by reaction hot pressing in vacuum. Appropriate quantities of the elemental Nb and Al powders were blended with the reinforcements (untreated or treated) in acetone. Elemental Nb powder with a median particle size of 10.6 μm and Al powder with a median particle size of 6.4 μm were used with M grade SiC whiskers having an aspect ratio of approximately 30 to produce composites. A liquid medium was used to help disperse the whiskers which have a tendency to clump up due to an electrostatic attraction between them. The blended mix was loaded into a graphite die for subsequent reaction hot pressing in vacuum. A boron-nitride coating was used on the die walls to minimize the reaction between the blended mix and the die. The composites were fabricated by consolidating the blended mix under appropriate hot pressing cycles discussed later.

CHARACTERIZATION

The fabricated composites were cleaned and density measurements were taken using the Archimedes principle. Specimens were cut, mounted and polished with diamond paste for microscopy examinations and microhardness testing. Crack lengths were measured from the hardness indents and were used for fracture toughness comparisons. X-ray diffraction (XRD) was performed on samples from each composite to identify various reaction products.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Initial compositions prior to the reaction hot pressing are included in Table 1. The density and hardness of the fabricated composites, designated as A, B, C, and D are also included in Table 1. The hot pressing cycle corresponding to each composite is shown in Fig. 1. Changes were made to each hot pressing cycle following the characterization of prior composites toward achieving greater densification. Low magnification optical micrographs (Fig. 2) of each composite show the extent of consolidation. Composite B shows the highest amount of consolidated area as a result of: a) a higher hot pressing temperature (1873 K), b) the application of pressure early in the hot pressing cycle (see Fig. 1), and c) the lack of whisker clumping.

Table 1. Properties of the composites fabricated by reaction hot pressing in vacuum.

Composite	Initial Composition (Wt %)	Density (g/cc)	Microhardness (HV) GPa **		Fracture Toughness Ratio (N/m) ^{1/2} ** K _{IC} /B(E) ^{1/2}
			mean	std. dev.	
A	Nb-77, Al-7, SiC-16	5.41	6.61	2.09	--
B	Nb-77, Al-7, SiC-16	6.84	14.48	1.22	277.01
C	Nb-64, Al-6, SiC* -16, Nb* -14	4.65	1.88	0.89	314.25
D	Nb-64, Al-6, SiC* -16, Nb* -14	4.80	3.53	1.17	--

* These refer to treated reinforcements.
 ** Of consolidated areas only.

Microprobe analysis of composite A led to the identification of several regions of different compositions in the consolidated areas (refer to Ref. 27 for more details). One region contained Nb and Al in compositions close to that of Nb₂Al, while another region contained Nb and Al with weight percentages of 60 and 40, respectively. Regions of pure Nb were also identified. XRD confirmed the presence of Nb₂Al, Nb and Nb₃Al in this composite. This compositional inhomogeneity partly explains the large standard deviation in the microhardness of composite A (see Table 1).

Figure 1. Reaction hot pressing (in vacuum) cycles used for fabricating niobium aluminide matrix composites identified as A, B, C and D. Initial compositions of composites are included in Table 1.

To increase the densification and the development of the intended intermetallic phase (Nb_3Al), it was deemed appropriate to apply pressure earlier in the hot pressing cycle along with an increase in the hot pressing temperature (see Fig. 1, composite B). The expected improvement in consolidation is achieved in composite B as evidenced by the optical micrographs (Fig. 2b) and an increase in density (Table 1). Detailed compositional analysis performed on composite B led to the identification of several reaction products (refer to Ref. 27 for more detail). The most important are the formation of niobium silicides and niobium carbide. The presence of SiC whiskers in the microstructure was not confirmed. It was felt that they reacted with the matrix materials to form the niobium carbide and niobium silicides. The microprobe analysis revealed the presence of Nb_5Si_3 , Nb_3Si and NbC . Subsequently this was confirmed by XRD.

The hot pressing cycle used for composite C was aimed at minimizing the reaction between the matrix and the reinforcements and yet increasing the densification. Composite C contains both treated SiC_w and treated Nb particles. The reinforcements were treated under appropriate temperatures and times, determined experimentally. The presence of the oxide layer on the whiskers was qualitatively confirmed by microprobe analysis and thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA). Upon completion of the treatment the reinforcements were blended with the elemental powders of Nb and Al in a shaker/mixer for fifteen minutes in an acetone solution. The blended material was consolidated in vacuum using the hot pressing cycle shown in Fig. 1 for composite C. Optical micrographs (Fig. 2) show that consolidation of composite C (Fig. 2c) is improved over that of composite A (Fig. 2a) but not over that of composite B (Fig. 2b). Microprobe analysis revealed the presence of different reaction products in composite C (refer to Ref. 27 for more detail). Compositions near that of Nb_3Al and Nb_2Al were identified in certain areas.

Figure 2. Optical micrographs a, b, c and d of composites A, B, C and D respectively, illustrating the extent of consolidation in each. Light areas represent fully consolidated regions while the dark areas represent poorly consolidated regions.

However many regions of poorly consolidated material containing mostly SiC whiskers were found in the microstructure (Ref. 27). XRD results confirmed the presence of Nb₃Al, Nb₂Al, NbC and SiC in composite C.

The preceding analysis indicated that the thickness of the oxide layer may not have been sufficient to completely protect the whiskers from reacting with the elemental Nb during hot pressing. Therefore the treatment temperature was increased, consistent with the work of Ribes et al. [28]. He reported an approximate 50 nm thick oxide layer on SiC particles after treatment for two hours at 1373 K. Also, a degassing step was added prior to hot pressing to remove absorbed species from the powders. The powder blend was degassed at 773 K for six hours. The pressure cycle for the hot pressing was kept unchanged but several changes were made to the temperature cycle for fabricating composite D (Fig. 1). These changes also took into account the anticipated temperature range (1023 to 1173 K) for the exothermic reaction between the Nb and Al [29,30]. A 30 minute hold time was placed at 823 K to ensure a uniform sample temperature. Above this temperature when the exothermic reaction is expected to occur, the temperature of the sample may increase substantially (a few hundred degrees) for a short time period as the molten Al reacts with the solid Nb particles to form an intermetallic compound. Subsequently, the temperature recedes and further densification has to be accomplished by diffusion. Temperatures around 70 to 80 % of T_m are needed for this to be effective. This means that after the exothermic reaction takes place, not much if any densification is taking place until higher temperatures are reached. Therefore the heating rate through this period was increased to reduce the time of the hot pressing cycle.

Consolidation of composite D improved over composite C as shown by a 3.2 % increase in density (Table 1). The composite still contains some poorly consolidated regions consisting mostly of SiC whiskers. This is attributed to whisker-to-whisker bonding that may have taken place between the whiskers during the oxide treatment, thereby resulting in poor dispersion of the whiskers into the matrix during blending and leading to large clumps of whiskers throughout the composite. XRD analysis performed on this sample showed the presence of Nb₃Al, Nb₂Al, NbC, NbO, and Nb. The XRD pattern for this composite matched very well with a pattern produced by Muruges et al. [31] for hot pressed Nb₃Al.

The indentations on the consolidated areas qualitatively point toward improved ductility/toughness of composites C and D in comparison with composites A and B (Fig. 3). Local yielding was observed at the edge of an indent in composite C (see Ref. 27). The cracks produced by the indentations were used to determine an apparent fracture toughness ratio for composites B and C. Small size of the consolidated regions precluded such determinations for composites A and D. Fracture toughness can be calculated by producing cracks by indentation and then using Eqn (1) [32]:

$$K_{Ic} = \xi \left(\frac{E}{H} \right)^{1/2} \frac{P}{c^{3/2}} \quad (1)$$

where,	K _{Ic} = mode I fracture toughness	P = indent load
	E = Young's modulus	c = half crack length
	H = hardness	ξ = material independent constant

Table 1 includes the calculated fracture toughness ratios obtained from Eqn (1). Composite B was indented with a load of 1 kg to produce radial cracks (Fig. 4), but a smaller load of 0.1 kg had to be used for composite C due to the relatively small size of the consolidated regions. The results (see Table 1) showed an increase of up to 45% in the fracture toughness of composite C, containing the treated reinforcements, relative to that of composite B, assuming that the constant ξ has the same value for both composites. Also, it was assumed that the consolidated regions of both composites have the same stiffness. Since the composites are not fully consolidated, no attempt has been made to determine the pertinent values of ξ and E. The comparatively high fracture toughness of the consolidated region in composite C is consistent with microstructural observation of plastic deformation at the indentations and relatively low hardness. Thus, it is

deemed appropriate to suggest that the room temperature ductility/toughness can be substantially improved by incorporating treated reinforcements in niobium aluminide matrix composites.

Figure 3. Microhardness indentations on the consolidated regions of composites A, B, C and D using a 0.1 kg load. Micrographs a, b, c and d represent composites A, B, C and D, respectively.

Figure 4. Microhardness indentation (1 kg load) in composite B showing radial-cracks that are used in determining the fracture toughness of the consolidated regions.

CONCLUSIONS

Oxide-coated SiC whiskers and Nb particles have been used to fabricate discontinuously reinforced niobium aluminide matrix composites by reaction hot pressing in vacuum. Process parameters have been optimized for the *in situ* formation of the Nb₃Al matrix while reducing adverse reactions between the reinforcements and the matrix. Based on the microstructural characteristics, microhardness, and the apparent mode I fracture toughness (determined by indentation method) it is concluded that the use of the treated reinforcements leads to an improvement (up to 45%) in fracture toughness of the composite in comparison with the untreated SiC whisker reinforced composite.

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